

Fermat's Principle, Particles with Rest Mass and Quantum Mechanics

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In a previous note (1) we argued that Fermat's least time principle applied to light involved finding an expression for time in terms of spatial variables and the taking of d/dx where x is an invariant spatial variable in the problem. For example, for reflection from a stationary or constantly moving mirror in the y direction or refraction with different $n(i)$ (indices of refraction in the y direction) x is invariant because there is no medium discontinuity in the x direction. We argued that Fermat's principle is equivalent to a conservation law in the direction of the invariant variable and that this conservation is in fact that of momentum in this direction. In (2) we argued that $E=pc$ with $c=x/t$ i.e. the wave dispersion equation for light contains Fermat's principle because one may write it as $0 = -Et + px$ and apply d/dx using $t(x)$ with x being the invariant variable. With conservation of momentum in the x direction and $E_1 = E_2$ for the two rays: $dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = 0$ for a two ray problem.

Fermat's principle and $E=pc$ pertain to light. The latter may be written as $0 = -Et + px$ ((1)) for light with $x/t=c$ which as we argued above leads to Fermat's principle if one takes d/dx for two rays. One may note, however, that one also obtains Fermat's principle for constant $= -Et + px$ with momentum conservation in the x direction. Furthermore a particle with rest mass bouncing off a floor may behave like light. This we argue leads to the idea of considering two different frames. For light $-E_1 t_1 + p_1 x_1 = 0 = -Et + px$ with $x/t = x_1/t_1 = c$.

For a particle with rest mass $-m_0 t_1 + 0 = -Et + px$ with $x/t=v$ where $c=1$ and m_0 is energy in a rest frame. (This is in fact the idea of a Lorentz invariant.) Thus Fermat's principle for a free particle seems to appear in the form $-Et + px = \text{constant}$. The constant is 0 for light.

The form $-Et + px$ is consistent with a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and a frequency to $1/E$ not only for light, but for the particle with rest mass. We argue that light moving in a medium is a complicated statistical process of scattering, but that the problem is treated in a "thermodynamical" manner by characterizing the medium by a single number i.e. single piece of information, namely the index of refraction i.e. $c \rightarrow c/n$ and $p \rightarrow pn$ for light. We argue that movement within the medium is like moving in a kind of constant potential for light. $-Et + (pn) x$ still holds and there is still conservation of momentum in the x direction for two media. Thus the idea of $d/dx \rightarrow p$ is already present in the photon form $-Et + px$ which follows from Maxwell's equations, but could also be derived from Fermat's principle as argued in (2). In other words, ideas of quantum mechanics for a particle with rest mass could ultimately follow from Fermat's principle, we argue.

A free particle with rest mass is linked with constant $= -Et + px$ and if one wishes to have an eigenfunction of momentum then: $-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. For a constant potential, just like with light, p would change, but the form $\exp(ipx)$ would remain. Thus it seems that even in average situations (like refraction) one still wants to have a periodic type spatial function $W(x)$ such that $-\hbar^2 d^2/dx^2 W(x) / W(x) = \langle pp \rangle$ such that $\langle pp \rangle / 2m + V(x) = E$ for a particle with rest mass. This is the Schrodinger equation and it is found mathematically that only certain E_n are allowed if one wishes to have specific boundary conditions like $W(x) \rightarrow 0$ at \pm infinite for say an oscillator problem. Thus we argue that the fundamental idea of taking a derivative of an invariant spatial variable in Fermat's principle which automatically yields conservation of

momentum is a basic idea found in quantum mechanics even for a particle with rest mass, namely that d/dx is associated with momentum. Mathematically d/dx is a translation operator and so the link with Fermat's principle shows how translation is linked with a spatially invariant spatial variable e.g. x .

Furthermore Fermat's principle shows that even complicated statistical scattering problems such as refraction (in which the photon scatters off of different molecules in different media) can be reduced to a periodic average problem with $p \rightarrow p_n$. This suggests that for a particle with a rest mass in a potential $V(x)$ one should also have a periodic spatial variable such that d/dx d/dx is linked to average momentum, we argue.

Fermat's Principle

Fermat's least time principle (or extremization of light) requires that one write an expression for time in terms of distance divided by speed of light. One then takes a derivative of a spatially invariant variable and sets it equal to 0. This approach is often applied to two ray problems such as scattering from a stationary mirror or one moving with speed v in the negative y direction or refraction with different media in the y direction. X is a spatially invariant variable because there is no discontinuity of medium in the x direction, only in the y . In (1) we showed explicitly that $dt_1/dx + d t_2/dx = 0 \rightarrow f_1 \sin(A) = f_2 \sin(B)$ i.e. Fermat's principle is equivalent to a conservation equation in the direction of the spatially invariant variable namely x . We also argued that this conservation equation is that of momentum in the spatially invariant direction. (Note A, B incident and reflected/refracted angles are measured with respect to y so $\sin(A), \sin(B)$ yields x projections.)

$E=pc$

In (2) we argued that Fermat's principle is contained in $E=pc$ if one writes $c=x/t$. Then one has:

$0 = -Et + (p_x)x + (p_y)y$ ((2)) which may be written for two rays. Taking d/dx and assuming $t(x)$:

$0 = -E_1 dt_1/dx + (p_1)_x - E_2 dt_2/dx + (p_2)_x$ ((3))

Using conservation of momentum in the direction of the invariant variable and assuming $E_1=E_2$ which holds for refraction and reflection from a stationary mirror then: $dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = 0$.

For a mirror moving with a constant v in the y direction E_1 is not equal to E_2 , but one may reformulate $E=pc$ i.e. replace it with $E_{\text{special}} = p v(\text{relative } a)$ where $v(\text{relative } a) = c - v \cos(A)$ for the incident ray and $v(\text{relative } b) = c + v \cos(B)$ for the reflected. Then $E_{\text{special}}(a) = E_{\text{special}}(b)$ as shown in (2).

Particle with Rest Mass

We argued above that conservation of momentum in the direction of a spatially invariant space variable is equivalent to conservation of momentum in that direction. Also Fermat's

principle predicts that the angle of incidence equals that of reflection for a stationary mirror. Such results should also hold for a particle with rest mass, but $E=pc$ clearly doesn't. Yet we argued that $E=pc$ contains Fermat's principle. As shown in the above section, however, we took derivatives with respect to x i.e. d/dx and a $(px)x$ yielded conserved momentum.

Thus the form

$$\text{constant} = -Et + (px)x + (py)y + (pz)z \quad ((5))$$

would also yield Fermat's principle. The constant happens to be 0 for a photon, but one may postulate that it is not zero for a particle with rest mass. What is the constant? Consider two frames of reference for light. Maxwell's equations suggest that the speed of light is the same as viewed from both. Then:

$$0 = -Et + px = -E_1 t_1 + p_1 x_1 \quad \text{with } x/t = x_1/t_1 = c \quad ((6))$$

For a particle with rest mass one may consider a frame in which the particle is at rest i.e. $p=0$ and $x=0$, $t=t_0$ and one in which it is moving with $x_1/t_1=v$ Then:

$$-m_0 c^2 t_0 = -E_1 t_1 + p_1 x_1 \quad \text{if } m_0 c^2 \text{ is rest energy (we use } c=1) \quad ((7))$$

Thus the form $-Et+px$ may pertain to both light and a particle with rest mass. It is in fact a Lorentz invariant, but no mention of special relativity has been made. In fact one may solve a constantly moving mirror problem using either Fermat's principle OR Lorentz transformations.

Quantum Mechanics

We ask in this section whether any ideas pertaining to light and Fermat's principle suggest quantum mechanical results for a particle with rest mass. First we note that the wave form $-Et+px=0$ suggests a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and a frequency to $1/E$. The fact that $E=pc$ is a separate issue. In the above section we argued that $-Et+px$ also holds for a particle with rest mass so this should also have a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and a frequency to $1/E$. Furthermore we argued that Fermat's principle already yields the important relationship:

$$d/dx \rightarrow p \quad ((8))$$

If one wishes to have a periodic eigenfunction then: $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((9))$

It may be noted that d/dx is a translation operator so Fermat's principle shows clearly why translation is needed: one needs invariant translation to have conservation of momentum in that direction.

Fermat's principle applied to refraction seems to be interesting. Different media contain different molecules and so a complicated statistical process of light scattering off these molecules/electrons etc occurs. One, however, treats the problem as in thermodynamics assuming that one parameter may describe the situation because the medium is the same

throughout. This is an “information” type of argument. Furthermore Fermat’s principle should still apply i.e. there should be conservation of momentum in the x direction. Thus the complicated scattering problem is still described by $-Et+px$, but $p \rightarrow pn$ in each medium where n is the index of refraction in the medium. Thus we suggest that light moving in a new medium is like motion in a kind of potential for light. The same idea holds for a free particle in a constant potential. Thus if a potential is present, one hypothesizes that:

- A. In a potential, a particle with rest mass should still be described by a spatial function $W(x)$ such that $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W = \langle pp \rangle$ where $\frac{1}{2m} \langle pp \rangle + V(x) = \text{Energy}$. ((9))

This is the Schrodinger time-independent equation which we argue follows from momentum being associated with d/dx in Fermat’s principle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $E=pc$ for light may be written as $0 = -Et+px$ where $x/t=c$. Fermat’s principle is contained in this expression because one may write it for two rays and take d/dx with conservation of momentum in the x direction holding. This yields: $dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx=0$ i.e. Fermat’s principle of $E_1=E_2$. We note that constant = $-Et+px$ also yields Fermat’s principle and suggest that a nonzero constant pertains to a particle with rest mass which also has conservation of momentum and behaves like light when bouncing off of a stationary mirror. Thus we argue that $d/dx \rightarrow p$ is already present in Fermat’s principle. This shows why d/dx , a mathematical translation operator, is present. It is associated with a spatially invariant variable namely x in Fermat’s principle.

We further argue that Fermat’s principle applied to refraction is a thermodynamic type problem because the medium is characterized by a single index of refraction (i.e. one piece of information) even though complicated statistical scattering occurs. The result is $p \rightarrow pn$. Thus a periodic form still holds for the photon Electric field proportional to $\cos(-Et+px)$ only p is modified even for an “average” type of scenario. We suggest that a constant potential for a particle with rest mass would lead to a similar result. Thus we postulate that if d/dx is linked to p then there exists a function $W(x)$ such that:

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W + V(x) = E$$

This is the time-independent Schrodinger equation, but developed using ideas from Fermat’s principle i.e $d/dx \rightarrow p$ and a distribution function $W(x)$ on which d/dx acts similar to the $\cos(-Et+px)$ for the electric field for light.

References

- 1 Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lack of Information / Invariance / Conservation and Reflection/Refraction Part II Discontinuity in Space = Time Reversal Break = Conservation Break (preprint, zenodo, 2022)

2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Is Fermat's Principle Contained in $E = pc$? (preprint, zenodo, 2022)